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Research Article

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF DICLOFENAC SODIUM SUSTAINED RELEASE TABLET

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The present study involves the formulation and evaluation of Diclofenac Sodium sustained release tablets using various polymers in different ratios to achieve prolonged drug release and enhanced patient compliance. Polymers such as Hydroxypropyl Methylcellulose (HPMC), Ethyl Cellulose (EC), and Sodium carboxy methyl cellulose were employed as release-retarding agents. A total of nine formulations (DS1 to DS9) were prepared by the direct compression method and evaluated for pre-compression and post-compression parameters including angle of repose, bulk density, tablet hardness, friability, weight variation, drug content, and in vitro drug release studies.

All the evaluated parameters were found to be within acceptable limits as per Indian Pharmacopoeia (IP) standards, indicating the suitability of the formulation process. Among the nine formulations, DS4 was identified as the optimized formulation, as it demonstrated a sustained drug release of 99.57% over 12 hours, following controlled release kinetics. The optimized formulation exhibited consistent matrix integrity and desirable drug release profile.

The study concludes that a suitable combination of polymers in appropriate ratios can effectively sustain the release of Diclofenac Sodium, making it a promising approach for once-daily oral administration.

Keywords: Diclofenac Sodium, HPMC, Ethyl Cellulose, and Sodium carboxy methyl cellulose

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1.INTRODUCTION:

Sustained release tablets are commonly taken only once or twice daily, compared with counterpart conventional forms that may have to take three or four times daily to achieve the same therapeutic effect. The advantage of administering a single dose of a drug that is released over an extended period of time to maintain a near-constant or uniform blood level of a drug often translates into better patient compliance, as well as enhanced clinical efficacy of the drug for its intended use. [1-6]

The first sustained release tablets were made by Howard Press in New Jersey in the early 1950's. The first tablets released under his process patent were called 'Nitroglyn' and made under license by Key Corp. in Florida.

Sustained release, prolonged release, modified release, extended release or depot formulations are terms used to identify drug delivery systems that are designed to achieve or extend therapeutic effect by continuously releasing medication over an extended period of time after administration of a single dose. The goal in designing sustained or sustained delivery systems is to reduce the frequency of the dosing or to increase effectiveness of the drug by localization at the site of action, reducing the dose required or providing uniform drug delivery. So, sustained release dosage form is a dosage form that release one or more drugs continuously in predetermined pattern for a fixed period of time, either systemically or to a specified target organ. [7-8] Sustained release dosage forms provide a better control of plasma drug levels, less dosage frequency, less side effect, increased efficacy and constant delivery. There are certain considerations for the preparation of extended release formulations:

- If the active compound has a long half-life, it is sustained on its own,
- If the pharmacological activity of the active is not directly related to its blood levels,
- If the absorption of the drug involves an active transport and
- If the active compound has very short half-life then it would require a large amount of drug to maintain a prolonged effective dose.

The above factors need serious review prior to design.

Introduction of matrix tablet as sustained release (SR) has given a new breakthrough for novel drug delivery system in the field of pharmaceutical technology. It excludes complex production procedures such as coating and Palettization during manufacturing and drug release rate from the dosage form is controlled mainly by the type and proportion of polymer used in the preparations. Hydrophilic polymer matrix is widely used for formulating an SR

dosage form. Because of increased complication and expense involved in marketing of new drug entities, has focused greater attention on development of sustained release or controlled release drug delivery systems. Matrix systems are widely used for the purpose of sustained release. It is the release system which prolongs and controls the release of the drug that is dissolved or dispersed [9].

In fact, a matrix is defined as a well-mixed composite of one or more drugs with gelling agent i.e. hydrophilic polymers. By the sustained release method therapeutically effective concentration can be achieved in the systemic circulation over an extended period of time, thus achieving better compliance of patients. Numerous SR oral dosage forms such as membrane control system, matrices with water soluble/insoluble polymers or waxes and osmotic systems have been developed, intense research has recently focused on the designation of SR systems for poorly water- soluble drugs.

Rationale for extended released dosage forms:

Some drugs are inherently long lasting and require only once-a-day oral dosing to sustain adequate drug blood levels and the desired therapeutic effect. These drugs are formulated in the conventional manner in immediate release dosage forms. However, many other drugs are not inherently long lasting and require multiple daily dosing to achieve the desired therapeutic results. Multiple daily dosing is inconvenient for the patient and can result in missed doses, made up doses, and noncompliance with the regimen [10-11].

When conventional immediate-release dosage forms are taken on schedule and more than once daily, they cause sequential therapeutic blood level peaks and valleys (troughs) associated with the taking of each dose. However, when doses are not administered on schedule, the resulting peaks and valleys reflect less than optimum drug therapy. For example, if doses are administered too frequently, minimum toxic concentrations of drug may be reached, with toxic side effects resulting. If doses are missed, periods of sub therapeutic drug blood levels or those below the minimum effective concentration may result, with no benefit to the patient.

Extended-release tablets and capsules are commonly taken only once or twice daily, compared with counterpart conventional forms that may have to be taken three or four times daily to achieve the same therapeutic effect. Typically, extended-release products provide an immediate release of drug that promptly produces the desired therapeutic effect, followed by gradual release of additional amounts of drug to maintain this effect over a predetermined period.

The sustained plasma drug levels provided by extended-release products oftentimes eliminate the need for night dosing, which benefits not only the patient but the caregiver as well [12].

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials Diclofenac sodium ($\geq 98\%$ purity) was used as the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API), sourced from a certified supplier and tested for purity. HPMC K-100, Ethyl cellulose, sodium Carboxy Methyl Cellulose, polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP K15) magnesium stearate, Talc and Lactose. All materials were pharmaceutical grade.

METHODOLOGY

Analytical method development:

a) Determination of absorption maxima:

100mg of Diclofenac Sodium pure drug was dissolved in 15ml of Methanol and make up to 100ml with 0.1N HCL (stock solution-1). 10ml of above solution was taken and make up with 100ml by using 0.1 N HCL (stock solution-2 i.e., 100 μ g/ml). From this 10ml was taken and make up with 100 ml of 0.1 N HCL (10 μ g/ml). Scan the 10 μ g/ml using a double-beam UV/VIS spectrophotometer in the range of 200 – 400 nm.

b) Preparation calibration curve:

100mg of Diclofenac Sodium pure drug was dissolved in 15ml of Methanol and volume make up to 100ml with 0.1N HCL (stock solution-1). 10ml of above solution was taken and make up with 100ml by using 0.1 N HCL (Stock solution-2 i.e. 100 μ g/ml). From this take 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 ml of solution and make up to 10ml with 0.1N HCL to obtain 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 μ g/ml of Diclofenac Sodium per ml of solution. The absorbance of the above dilutions was measured at 276 nm by using UV-Spectrophotometer taking 0.1N HCL as blank. Then a graph was plotted by taking Concentration on X-Axis and Absorbance on Y-Axis which gives a straight-line Linearity of standard curve was assessed from the square of correlation coefficient (R^2) which determined by least-square linear

regression analysis. The above procedure was repeated by using pH 6.8 phosphate buffer solutions.

Drug – Excipient compatibility studies

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy:

Drug excipient interaction studies are significant for the successful formulation of every dosage form. Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy studies were used for the assessment of physicochemical compatibility and interactions, which helps in the prediction of interaction between drug and other excipients. In the current study 1:1 ratio was used for preparation of physical mixtures used for analyzing of compatibility studies. FT-IR studies were carried out with a Bruker, ATR FTIR facility using direct sample technique.

Formulation development of Sustained release Tablets:

All the formulations were prepared by direct compression method. The compositions of different formulations are given in Table. The tablets were prepared as per the procedure given below and aim is to prolong the release of Diclofenac Sodium.

Procedure:

- 1) Diclofenac Sodium and all other ingredients except Mg stearate and Talc were individually passed through sieve no # 40.
- 2) Ethyl cellulose, PVP K 15 and polymer mix thoroughly than add the binder solution mix properly up to 15 min.
- 3) Dry the above mixture at 65-70°C by using dryer.
- 4) After completion of drying the mixture is passed through sieve no #22.
- 5) The powder mixture was lubricated with Mg stearate and Talc.
- 6) Finally go for compression.

Table No :1. Formulation of Sustained release tablets

Formulation code	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7	D8	D9
Diclofenac Sodium	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
HPMC K-100	25	50	75	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ethyl cellulose	-	-	-	25	50	75	-	-	-
Sodium carboxy methyl cellulose	-	-	-	-	-	-	25	50	75
PVP K 15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
Magnesium Stearate	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Talc	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Lactose	94	69	44	94	69	44	94	69	44
Total weight	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

Evaluation Parameters**Pre Compression parameters****Bulk density (D_B)**

Bulk density is the ratio between a given mass of the powder and its bulk volume.

Bulk density = Mass of Powder / Bulk volume of the powder

Bulk density (D_B) = W / V_0

Procedure: An accurately weighed quantity of granules (w) (which was previously passed through sieve No: 40) was carefully transferred into 250 ml measuring cylinder and measure the bulk volume.

Tapped Density (D_T)

Tapped density is the ratio between a given mass of powder (or) granules and the constant (or) fixed volume of powder or granules after tapping.

Tapped density = mass of the powder/ tapped volume

Procedure: An accurately weighed quantity of granules (w) (which was previously passed through sieve No: 40) was carefully transferred into 250 ml measuring cylinder and the cylinder was tapped on a wooden surface from the height of 2.5 cm at two second intervals. The tapping was continued until no further change in volume (until a constant volume) was obtained (V_f). The tapped density was calculated by using the formula

Tapped density (D_T) = W / V_f

Hausner's ratio**Flow property**

Hausner's ratio is an indirect index of ease of powder flow and was calculated by the formula,

Hausner's ratio = D_T / D_B

Where, D_T is the tapped density

D_B is the bulk density

Compressibility index

Compressibility index (CI) was determined by measuring the initial volume (V_0) and final volume (V_f) after hundred tapping's of a sample in a measuring cylinder. It indicates the powder flow properties and expressed in terms of percentage and given in table no. 14 and calculated by using the formula

$$\% \text{ Compressibility index} = \frac{V_0 - V_f}{V_0} \times 100$$

Angle of repose

Angle of repose was measured by fixed funnel method. It determines flow property of the powder. It is defined as maximum angle formed between the surface of the pile of powder and the horizontal plane.

The powder was allowed to flow through the funnel fixed to a stand at definite height (h). By measuring the height and radius of the heap of powder formed (r), angle of repose was calculated by using formula given below and the calculated values obtained was shown in table no. 14

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} (h / r)$$

Where, θ is the angle of repose

h is the height in cm

r is the radius in cm

Table no.2 :The flow property of powder blend

Flow property	Angle of repose	Compressibility index (%)	Hausner's ratio
Excellent	25-30	<10	1.00-1.11
Good	31-35	11-15	1.12-1.18
Fair	36-40	16-20	1.19-1.25
Passable	41-45	21-25	1.26-1.34
Poor	46-55	26-31	1.35-1.45
Very poor	56-65	32-37	1.46-1.59
Very very poor	>66	>38	>1.60

Post Compression parameters**Weight variation test**

Twenty tablets were randomly selected and weighed, to estimate the average weight and that were compared with individual tablet weight. The percentage weight variation was calculated as per Indian Pharmacopoeia Specification. Tablets with an average weight 250 mg so the % deviation was ± 5 %.

Table no.3: IP standards of uniformity of weight

S. No.	Average weight of tablet	% of deviation
1	≤ 80 mg	10
2	> 80 mg to <250 mg	7.5
3	≥ 250 mg	5

Friability test

Twenty tablets were weighed and subjected to drum of friability test apparatus. The drum rotated at a speed of 25 rpm. The friabilator was operated for 4 minutes and reweighed the tablets. % loss (F) was calculated by the following formula.

$$F = 100 (W_0 - W) / W_0$$

Where W_0 = Initial weight, W = Final weight

Hardness test

The hardness of tablets was measured by using Monsanto hardness tester. The results were complied with IP specification.

Thickness test

The rule of physical dimension of the tablets such as sizes and thickness is necessary for consumer acceptance and maintain tablet uniformity. The dimensional specifications were measured by using screw gauge. The thickness of the tablet is mostly related to the tablet hardness can be used as initial control parameter.

Drug content

The amount of drug in tablet was important for to monitor from tablet to tablet, and batch to batch is to evaluate for efficacy of tablets. For this test, take ten tablets from each batch were weighed and powdered. Weighed equivalent to the average weight of the tablet powder and transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask and dissolved in a suitable quantity of media. The solution was made up to the mark and mixed well. Then filter the solution. A portion of the filtrate sample was analyzed by UV spectrophotometer.

In vitro drug release studies

Apparatus	--	USP-II, Paddle Method
Dissolution Medium	--	0.1 N HCL, p H 6.8 Phosphate buffer
RPM	--	50
Sampling intervals (hrs)	--	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 12hrs.
Temperature	--	37°C ± 0.5°C

Procedure:

900ml of 0.1 HCL was placed in vessel and the USP apparatus –II (Paddle Method) was assembled. The media was allowed to equilibrate to temp of 37°C ±

0.5°C. Tablet was placed in the vessel and apparatus was operated for 2 hours. Then 0.1 N HCL was replaced with pH 6.8 phosphate buffer and process was continued up to 24 hrs at 50 rpm. At specific time intervals, withdrawn 5 ml of sample and again 5ml media was added to maintain the sink condition. Withdrawn samples were analyzed at 276 nm wavelength of drug using UV-spectrophotometer.

Application of Release Rate Kinetics to Dissolution Data

Various models were tested for explaining the kinetics of drug release. To analyze the mechanism of the drug release rate kinetics of the dosage form, the obtained data were fitted into zero-order, first order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer-Peppas release model.

Zero order release rate kinetics:

To study the zero-order release kinetics the release rate data are fitted to the following equation.

$$F = K_0 t$$

Where, 'F' is the drug release at time 't', and 'K₀' is the zero order release rate constant. The plot of % drug release versus time is linear.

First order release rate kinetics: The release rate data are fitted to the following equation

$$\text{Log}(100-F) = kt$$

A plot of log cumulative percent of drug remaining to be released vs. time is plotted then it gives first order release.

Higuchi release model: To study the Higuchi release kinetics, the release rate data were fitted to the following equation.

$$F = k t^{1/2}$$

Where, 'k' is the Higuchi constant.

In higuchi model, a plot of % drug release versus square root of time is linear.

Korsmeyer and Peppas release model:

The mechanism of drug release was evaluated by plotting the log percentage of drug released versus log time according to Korsmeyer- Peppas equation. The exponent 'n' indicates the mechanism of drug release calculated through the slope of the straight Line.

$$M_t / M_\infty = K t^n$$

Where, M_t/M_∞ is fraction of drug released at time 't', k represents a constant, and 'n' is the diffusional exponent, which characterizes the type of release mechanism during the dissolution process. For non-Fickian release, the value of n falls between 0.5 and 1.0; while in case of Fickian diffusion, $n = 0.5$; for zero-order release (case I transport), $n=1$; and for super case II transport, $n > 1$. In this model, a plot of $\log(M_t/M_\infty)$ versus $\log(\text{time})$ is linear.

3.RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

The present work was designed to develop sustained tablets of Diclofenac Sodium using various polymers. All the formulations were evaluated for

physicochemical properties and *in vitro* drug release studies.

Analytical Method

Standard graph of Diclofenac Sodium in 0.1N HCL:

The scanning of the 10 μ g/ml solution of Diclofenac Sodium the ultraviolet range (200-400nm) against 0.1 N HCL the maximum peak observed at λ_{max} as 276 nm. The standard concentration of Diclofenac Sodium (10 - 50 μ g/ml) was prepared in 0.1N HCL showed good linearity with R^2 value of 0.9998, which suggests that it obeys the Beer-Lamberts law.

Table no. 4: Standard curve of Diclofenac Sodium 0.1N HCL

Concentration (μ g/ mL)	Absorbance
0	0
10	0.114
20	0.218
30	0.335
40	0.439
50	0.548

Fig.1: Calibration curve of Diclofenac Sodium 0.1N HCl at 276 nm

Standard Curve of Diclofenac Sodium Phosphate buffer pH 6.8

The scanning of the 10 μ g/ml solution of Diclofenac Sodium the ultraviolet range (200-400nm) against 6.8 pH phosphate the maximum peak observed at the λ_{max} as 278nm. The standard concentrations of Diclofenac Sodium (10 - 50 μ g/ml) prepared in 6.8 pH phosphate buffer showed good linearity with R^2 value of 0.9998, which suggests that it obeys the Beer-Lamberts law.

Table no. 5: Standard curve of Diclofenac Sodium Phosphate buffer pH 6.8

Concentration (μ g / ml)	Absorbance
0	0
10	0.147
20	0.284
30	0.419
40	0.559
50	0.693

Fig.no.2: Calibration of Diclofenac Sodium Phosphate buffer pH 6.8

4.EVALUATION PARAMETERS

Pre-compression parameters

Table no.6: Pre-compression parameters of powder blend

Formulation Code	Angle of Repose	Bulk density (gm/ml)	Tapped density (gm/ml)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's Ratio
DS1	25.01	0.59	0.57	14.03	1.16
DS2	26.8	0.46	0.67	16.41	1.19
DS3	27.7	0.32	0.54	18.75	1.23
DS4	25.33	0.54	0.64	15.62	1.18
DS5	25.24	0.52	0.65	18.46	1.22
DS6	28.12	0.46	0.56	15.15	1.17
DS7	27.08	0.58	0.69	15.94	1.18
DS8	25.12	0.48	0.67	15.78	1.18
DS9	26.45	0.54	0.65	16.92	1.25

Tablet powder blend was subjected to various pre-compression parameters. The angle of repose values was showed from 25.01 to 28.12; it indicates that the powder blend has good flow properties. The bulk density of all the formulations was found to be in the range of 0.32 to 0.59 (gm/cm³) showing that the powder has good flow properties. The tapped density of all the formulations was found to be in the range of 0.54 to 0.69 showing the powder has good flow properties. The compressibility index of all the formulations was found to ranging from 14.03 to 18.75 which showed that the powder has good flow properties. All the formulations were showed the Hausner ratio ranging from 1.16 to 1.25 indicating the powder has good flow properties.

Post Compression Parameters For tablets

Table.no 7: Post Compression Parameters of tablets

Formulation codes	Average Weight (mg)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (%loss)	Thickness (mm)	Drug content (%)
DS1	198.37	3.67±0.84	0.37	2.25±0.22	98.72
DS2	199.91	3.51±0.47	0.56	2.68±0.18	97.88
DS3	197.88	3.62±0.55	0.48	2.75±0.47	99.62
DS4	200.05	3.48±0.38	0.44	2.98±0.71	100.02
DS5	196.53	3.66±0.22	0.58	2.55±0.38	98.96
DS6	199.78	3.58±0.49	0.42	2.62±0.26	99.57
DS7	197.62	3.45±0.96	0.61	2.48±0.55	97.34
DS8	198.58	3.61±0.44	0.54	2.71±0.48	98.87
DS9	196.86	3.58±0.82	0.39	2.48±0.66	99.66

Weight variation and thickness: all the formulations were evaluated for uniformity of weight using electronic weighing balance and the results are shown in table 9.5. The average tablet weight of all the formulations was found to be between 196.53 to 200.05.

The maximum allowed percentage weight variation for tablets weighing >200 mg is 5% and no formulations are not exceeding this limit. Thus, all the formulations were found to comply with the standards given in I.P and thickness of all the formulations was also complying with the standards that were found to be between 2.25±0.22 to 2.98±0.71.

Hardness and friability:

All the formulations were evaluated for their hardness, using Monsanto hardness tester and the results are shown in table. The average hardness for all the formulations was found to be between (3.45±0.96 to 3.67±0.84) kg/cm² which was found to be acceptable.

Friability was determined to estimate the ability of the tablets to withstand the abrasion during packing,

handling and transporting. All the formulations were evaluated for their percentage friability using Roche friabilator and the results were shown in table. The average percentage friability for all the formulations was between 0.37 and 0.61, which was found to be within the limit.

Drug content: All the formulations were evaluated for drug content according to the procedure described in the methodology section and the results were shown in table. The drug content values for all the formulations were found to in range of (97.88 to 100.02). According to IP standards the tablets must contain not less than 95% and not more than 105% of the stated amount of the drug. Thus, all the FDT formulations comply with the standards given in IP.

4.4 In vitro drug release studies:

The formulations prepared with different polymers by direct compression method. The tablets dissolution study was carried out in paddle dissolution apparatus using 0.1 N HCL for 2 hr. and 6.8 pH phosphate buffer for remaining hours as a dissolution medium.

Table no.8: Dissolution Data of Diclofenac Sodium Tablets

Time (hrs)	Cumulative Percentage Drug Released								
	DS1	DS2	DS3	DS4	DS5	DS6	DS7	DS8	DS9
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	8.62	9.71	11.23	12.81	8.51	10.11	9.62	12.62	8.89
2	15.11	18.02	19.12	19.96	17.73	18.01	15.66	18.22	19.66
3	22.37	26.66	24.56	27.87	31.88	28.19	26.37	21.75	25.53
4	31.74	33.25	33.45	38.19	35.52	32.63	39.74	34.51	38.82
5	38.06	44.75	39.56	46.72	49.17	42.85	45.06	48.37	42.36
6	49.52	52.13	46.22	49.12	57.91	53.19	56.28	55.96	46.62
7	57.09	62.52	56.05	59.69	64.74	59.32	65.09	63.05	57.96
8	62.92	69.22	59.77	66.33	73.95	69.88	72.92	68.23	62.19
9	69.63	73.01	67.59	75.76	79.82	74.43	79.63	75.77	69.42
10	73.82	89.91	73.81	87.98	88.67	83.75	87.82	89.13	76.85
11	81.74	91.36	84.22	96.71	93.08	87.27	95.74	91.56	89.44
12	89.69	95.82	93.38	99.57	95.93	92.22	97.12	98.21	94.97

Figure 3: Dissolution study of Diclofenac Sodium Sustained Release tablets (DS1 to DS3)

Figure 4: Dissolution study of Diclofenac Sodium tablets (DS4 to DS6)

Figure 5: Dissolution study of Diclofenac Sodium tablets (DS7 to DS9)

Formulations prepared with HPMC K-100 retarded the drug release in the concentration of 50 mg (DS2 Formulation) showed required release pattern i.e., retarded the drug release up to 12 hours and showed maximum of 95.82% in 12 hours with good retardation

Formulations prepared with Ethyl cellulose retarded the drug release in the concentration of 25 mg (DS4 Formulation) showed required release pattern i.e., retarded the drug release up to 12 hours and showed maximum of 99.75 % in 12 hours with good retardation.

Formulations prepared with Sodium carboxy methyl cellulose retarded the drug release in the concentration of 50 mg (DS8 Formulation) showed required release pattern i.e., retarded the drug release

up to 12 hours and showed maximum of 98.21% in 12 hours with good retardation.

Among all the formulations DS4 formulation containing (Drug: Ethyl cellulose) 1:1 ratio showed maximum % drug release i.e. 99.75 % at 12 hr.

Hence based on dissolution data of 9 formulations, DS4 formulation showed better release up to 12 hours. So DS4 formulation is optimized formulation.

4.5 Application of Release Rate Kinetics to Dissolution Data

Data of *in vitro* release studies of formulations which were showing better drug release were fit into different equations to explain the release kinetics of Diclofenac Sodium release from sustained tablets. The data was fitted into various kinetic models such as zero, first order kinetics, Higuchi and Korsmeyer

peppas mechanisms and the results were shown in the below table.

Fig: 6 Graph of zero order kinetics

Table 9: Release Kinetics data for optimized formulation (DS4)

CUMULATIVE (%) RELEASE Q	TIME (T)	ROOT (T)	% RELEASE	LOG (T)	LOG REMAIN	RELEASE RATE (CUMULATIVE % RELEASE / t)	1/CUM% RELEASE	PEPPAS log Q/100	% Drug Remaining	Q01/3	Qt1/3	Q01/3-Qt1/3
0	0	0			2.000				100	4.642	4.642	0.000
12.81	1	1.000	1.108	0.000	1.940	12.810	0.0781	-0.892	87.19	4.642	4.434	0.207
19.96	2	1.414	1.300	0.301	1.903	9.980	0.0501	-0.700	80.04	4.642	4.310	0.332
27.87	3	1.732	1.445	0.477	1.858	9.290	0.0359	-0.555	72.13	4.642	4.163	0.479
38.19	4	2.000	1.582	0.602	1.791	9.548	0.0262	-0.418	61.81	4.642	3.954	0.688
46.72	5	2.236	1.670	0.699	1.727	9.344	0.0214	-0.330	53.28	4.642	3.763	0.879
49.12	6	2.449	1.691	0.778	1.707	8.187	0.0204	-0.309	50.88	4.642	3.706	0.936
59.69	7	2.646	1.776	0.845	1.605	8.527	0.0168	-0.224	40.31	4.642	3.429	1.213
66.33	8	2.828	1.822	0.903	1.527	8.291	0.0151	-0.178	33.67	4.642	3.229	1.412
75.76	9	3.000	1.879	0.954	1.385	8.418	0.0132	-0.121	24.24	4.642	2.894	1.748
87.98	10	3.162	1.944	1.000	1.080	8.798	0.0114	-0.056	12.02	4.642	2.291	2.351
96.71	11	3.317	1.985	1.041	0.517	8.792	0.0103	-0.015	3.29	4.642	1.487	3.154
99.57	12	3.464	1.998	1.079	0.540	8.298	0.0100	-0.002	0.43	4.642	0.755	3.887

Figure 7: Graph of Higuchi release kinetics

Figure 8: Graph of Peppas release kinetics

Figure 9: Graph of first order release kinetics

Based on the data above results the optimized formulation followed Kors Mayer Peppas Release Kinetics.

Drug and Excipient Compatibility Studies: FTIR study:

Fig. 10: FTIR Graph of Pure Drug

Fig. 11: FTIR graph of optimized Formulation

From the FTIR data was evident that the drug and excipient does not have any interactions. Hence, they were compatible.

5. CONCLUSION:

The present study successfully focused on the formulation and evaluation of Diclofenac Sodium sustained release tablets using different polymers such as Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC), Ethyl Cellulose (EC), and Sodium carboxy methyl cellulose in varying ratios. All the prepared formulations were evaluated for pre-compression and post-compression parameters, which were found to be within acceptable Pharmacopeial limits, indicating good flow properties and tablet integrity. Among all the formulations, the optimized batch (DS4) demonstrated a sustained drug release profile over 12 hours, with a cumulative drug release of approximately 99.57%. The drug release followed

zero-order kinetics with non-Fickian diffusion, confirming the sustained release behaviour. The combination and concentration of hydrophilic and hydrophobic polymers significantly influenced the drug release rate and matrix integrity.

Thus, it can be concluded that Diclofenac Sodium sustained release tablets can be effectively developed using a suitable combination of polymers, providing a prolonged therapeutic effect, reduced dosing frequency, and improved patient compliance.

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